

Paper 11

DEMONITISATION AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN ECONOMY**Mr. B. Sudheer Kumar**

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-Mail Id: - bskmba06@gmail.com**Abstract:**

On 8th November 2016, the Government of India announced the demonetization of all Rs.500 and Rs.1000 banknotes of the Mahatma Gandhi series. The government claimed that the action would curtail the shadow economy and crack down on the use of illicit and counterfeit cash to fund illegal activity and terrorism. The demonetization that happened will not only have economic impact but also social and political ramifications, both from immediate and long-term perspectives. This paper attempts to study impact of demonetization with reference to Common man. Through this article an attempt had been made to understand both its merits and demerits of demonetizations on Indian economy.

Keywords: Demonetization, Indian economy, Common man, Black Money, Corruption

1. INTRODUCTION:

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. It occurs whenever there is a change of national currency. The current form or forms of money is pulled from circulation and retired often to be replaced with new notes or coins. Such a step, for example, was taken when the European Monetary Union nations decided to adopt Euro as a currency. Zimbabwe, Fiji, Singapore and Philippines were other countries to have opted for currency demonetization. The demonetization of 500 and 1000 was a policy enacted by the Government of India on 8th November 2016. All 500 and 1000 banknotes of the Mahatma Gandhi series ceased to be legal tender in India from 9th November 2016. After the announcement that 500 and 1,000 rupee notes were no longer legal tender; people were given 50 days to deposit them in bank accounts or exchange them for new notes at banks and post offices, when only half of Indian adults have bank accounts. By withdrawing 86 percent of circulating currency when 70 to 80 percent of transactions are cash-based, the Indian government has burned down its economic house in order to eradicate the pest of corruption. According to The Reserve Bank of India, the most important reason for the demonetization of 500 and 1000 rupees note was the rise of fake currencies of the same notes, and also the higher occurrence of black money in the economy. "The fake notes are being used for illegal activities by anti-nationalists like terrorists and India being a nation of a cash-based economy, the circulation of fake currency continues to be a threat. But it has been taken care by Government that the public that a person who changed his higher value cash will get exactly the equal amount in lower denominations. Though people had time until the end of the year to deposit the notes in bank accounts, doing so in large quantities could expose them to high taxes and fines. So they rushed to gas pumps, banks, foreign-exchange counters, ATMs, to jewelry shops, and to creditors to repay loans.

2. HISTORY OF DEMONETISATION IN INDIA

The first demonetization was when Rs.1000, Rs.5000 and Rs.10,000 notes were taken out of circulation in January 1946 a year and a half before the country won independence from the British. The Rs.10,000 notes were the largest currency denomination ever printed by the Reserve Bank of India, introduced for the first time in 1938. All three notes were introduced in 1954. In the early 1970, the Wanchoo Committee, direct tax inquiry committee set up by the Government, suggested demonetization as a measure to unearth and counter the spread of Black Money. The move was called a „death blow“ to black marketers. The repercussions were similar to present demonetization with people dying of shock, exceptionally long lines at the banks and the middle classes being hit. Then in 1977, the Janta Party coalition government came into power. A year into the government’s term, party leader Morarji Desai was more bullish about cracking down on counterfeits and black money. The High Denomination Bank Notes (Demonetization) Act, instated by the ruling party on January 16th 1978, deemed the Rs.1,000, Rs. 5,000 and Rs.10,000 notes illegal for the second time. It was termed as “an Act to provide in the public interest for the demonetization of certain high denomination bank notes and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto”.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on Desk Research through collection of Secondary Data hence it is theoretical in nature with emphasis on Indian Economy. Following are the objectives of the study:

- ✓ To study the impact of demonetisation on common man.
- ✓ To study the impact of demonetisation on Indian Economy.
- ✓ To understand the impact of demonitisation on different industrial sectors.

Need for Demonetization

Demonetization is one of the Government’s bold steps towards transformation of Indian Economy. It is probably one of the biggest big-bang reforms undertaken by Government after a long time. In spite of many reasons quoted by Government, RBI in its FAQ on “Withdrawal of legal tender character of existing bank notes in the denomination of Rs. 500 and Rs. 1000” mentions reasons why this scheme is introduced. It reads as follows: “The incidence of fake Indian currency notes in higher denomination has increased. For ordinary persons, the fake notes look similar to genuine notes, even though no security feature has been copied. The fake notes are used for antinational and illegal activities. High denomination notes have been misused by terrorists and for hoarding black money. India remains a cash based economy hence the circulation of Fake Indian Currency Notes continues to be a menace. In order to contain the rising incidence of fake notes and black money, the scheme to withdraw has been introduced”.

Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi quoted the following reasons for demonetisation during a television address to the nation on 08.11.2016: “In a historical move that will add record strength in the fight against corruption, black money, money laundering, terrorism and financing of terrorists as well as counterfeit notes, the Government of India has decided that the five hundred and one thousand rupee notes will no longer be legal tender from midnight, 8th November 2016. The Government has accepted the recommendations of the RBI to issue Two thousand rupee notes and new notes of Five hundred rupees will also be placed in circulation.” One more reason for demonetization is to minimize Fiscal Deficit. It has subsidiary benefits as it will take out the counterfeit notes from circulation and the

unaccounted money, if does not come out, will be of no use. It will stop Hawala trade too. Some of the facts and figures to describe the existing parallel economy can be viewed and analysed as follows: First of all, if you look at our currency system, India is a cash-based society. 70% of values of transactions are in cash and even our gross domestic product (GDP), 45% of our GDP comes from informal sector. Informal sector accounts for 80% of our population.

4. IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION ON INDIAN ECONOMY

The demonetization is very important to everyone. Everyone got affected by this he/she might be a business man, salaried, housewife, students, working professionals, politicians etc.

5. POSITIVE IMPACTS

- For quite some time at least, people who are involved in counterfeit currency and terrorism will not be able to continue it further. The smuggling of arms and dealing with the terrorist will not sustain further as all the money will be on record now.
- It will drastically affect the corrupt practices. People who are holding black money in cash will not be able to exchange much as they would be in a fear of getting penalized by authorities.
- It will certainly flush out a good chunk of black money hoarded in currency notes of such denominations (Rs.500 and Rs.1000).
- Decline in inflationary pressure as demand along with household inflation expectations are likely to go down. This would make RBI more comfortable on managing inflation in future increasing the possibility of rate cuts.
- Government revenue will boost up as more earnings will be declared
- Collection of higher taxes will help in nation building like development of roads, infrastructure, transportation and many others.
- People who have opened Jan Dhan accounts under the Prime Minister Jan Dhan Yojna, can now deposit their cash under this scheme and this money can be used for implementation of national developmental projects which will demand more labor and other skilled manpower which will give rise to employment opportunities.
- Cash in system will boost educational loans and business loans thus bringing more opportunities.
- Substantial increase in the demand of digital transactions, E-Wallets, usage of plastic money, online transactions using E-banking etc.

6. NEGATIVE IMPACTS :

- Commodity and general cash market transactions felt an immediate impact. There is a disruption in current liquidity situation, as households are likely to get affected by the note exchange and currency withdrawals terms laid by the government.
- Economy has already borne short-term costs such as the time people wasted in long ques, liquidity crisis in the informal economy, the worker layoffs and many tragic deaths.
- Certain sections of the society namely agriculture sector, small traders, households, daily wage earners etc faced short-term disruptions due to absence of liquid cash.

- GDP formation will be affected with the reduction in consumption demand and negative impact on disposable income.
- Land parcels are usually paid in cash. With restrictions on cash transactions, land prices would fall. As smaller/unorganized players get affected, demand for real estate may decline.
- There would be negative impact on NBFC"s that make disbursements in cash and do most of their collections in cash. These include gold financing companies, micro finance institutions etc.
- There will be added replacement costs of currency. Increased cost of operating ATM"s need to be refilled more often and also it will be a huge burden on banks. Moreover disruption of old currency units and printing of new currency will involve costs, which has to be borne by government and if costs are higher than the benefits then there is no use of demonetization.
- Demonetization itself will not fight black income. The most important policy should be tax administration where the tax authorities can monitor expenditure and matching it with income of the respective individuals.
- Professor Arun Kumar, Jawaharlal Nehru University, is of the view that demonetization is no silver bullet against fake currency. Fresh printing and import of counterfeit currency will not stop with demonetization.
- Though Digitization may be a positive effect of demonetization, India to become cash less economy will take time. Bloomberg data shows the share of cash in the volume of consumer transactions is 98% and much of the cash transactions are in rural India. PwC Report showed that India's unbanked population still stood at 233 million, suggesting that much remains to be done before people can be on boarded on to the digital bandwagon.

Indirect Effect of the Demonetization:

1. Assets in the form of Cash or Gold and Silver seized during demonetization period i.e. November and December through raids.
2. Action on "Benami Property" under the "Benami Transactions (Prohibition) Amendment Act, 2016" is expected to take place which will be the toughest attack on black money and corruption in India.
3. Rising Digital payments are due to demonetization. During the period of November and December 2016, people faced cash-crunch and they found the digital payment problem solving.
4. After 08th November 16, the RBI, Income Tax department and other Central Government departments have announced different rules and restrictions on cash transaction. This has positively affected the mindset of people in India against accumulation of Black money through corruption and other unfair means. This can be termed as "Psychological effect of demonetization on Black Money".

5. **IMPACT OF DEMONITISATION ON DIFFERENT SECTORS::**
 Demonetization created effect on different sectors in different manners resulting into boom for some sectors like E-Wallet businesses and somewhere resulting into temporary slowdown like micro businesses like vegetable vendors or some small

seasonal businesses, where most of the transactions are on cash basis. Some of the sectors having major effect of demonitisation are covered for the study

Domestic/Household Sector: The logic behind this demonetization is to curb the use of these high value notes in the black money market. Now almost everyone has Rs1000/500 notes so now it would become difficult for the common people to do their business/ household works easily.

Reduce Government Liability It will reduce the risk and cost of cash handling as soft money is safer than hard money. It will also reduce government liability. Since every note is a liability for the government, the old currency will become worthless for those people, who choose not to disclose their income. Thus, this will extinguish government's liability to that extent.

Health care sector:

The impact on the health care sector was huge with most of the hospitals refused to accept the old currency. The issue was faced by the Union Minister Mr. Sidharamaiah in Bengaluru when the hospital administration refused to accept the old currency to retrieve his brother's dead body. The common man faced severe issues transacting in the hospitals with old currencies and several cases of death have been registered for not attending the patients due to demonetization.

Farming and fishing industry Farmers generally deal in cash . The poor people through middlemen are getting their currencies exchanged for Rs.300 or Rs.400. Farmers have difficulty buying seeds and fertilizer and selling crops and perishable products. The demonetisation led to unavailability of cash to pay for food products. The reduction in demand that arose in turn led to a crash in the prices of crops. Farmers were unable to recover even the costs of transportation from their fields to the market from the low prices offered. This forced the farmers across the country to dump their products in desperation. Some farmers resorted to burying unsold vegetables. Agricultural products such as vegetables, food grains, sugarcane, milk and eggs were dumped on roads. The fishing industry which depends on cash sales of freshly caught fish was close to collapse.

Impact on Common man: The demonetization has a positive impact on the common people that now they the use of digital currencies got increased. So the people no need to carry physical currencies to any places which also reduced the crime rate. The price of some of the important commodities got decreased.

E-Business

E-commerce companies saw up to a 30% decline in cash on delivery (COD) orders. Several e-commerce companies hailed the demonetization decision as an impetus to an increase in digital payments. They believe that it would lead to a decline in COD returns which is expected to cut down their costs. The demand for point of sales (POS) or card swipe machines has increased. The goods and services tax (GST), whose objective is to replace all taxes levied by the federal government and the states with one central tax.

Jewelry and Real Estate Business The liquidity squeeze caused by demonetisation will be negative across sectors with high level of cash transactions. Real estate, jewellery, retailing, restaurants, logistics, consumer durables and luxury brands, cement and some segments in retail/SME lending space will be facing short term instability. Those companies with high level of debt will face more pressure and can face loan defaults.

E-wallet firms could gain good business

A digital wallet is an electronic device which allows an individual to make electronic commerce transactions like payment of bills or online bookings etc. An individual's bank

account can also be linked to the digital wallet. The examples of wallet in India are- Paytm, PayU India, MobiKwik, and Free charge and so on. Such E-wallets are expected to be the biggest beneficiaries of the decision of demonetization taken by central government.

Impact on IT Industry

This step can bring grey market commodities / illegal money lending / money laundering etc., under control which is otherwise unmanageable. The IT industries prefer purchase and sales through banking system only. It won't curb grey channel market but will surely have an adverse effect on the products which are promoted by grey channel. This move will help brands to grow and helps in curbing the fake, grey market, and Chinese import cash sales. New-age payments like PayTM, Instamojo Payment Gateway, PayUMoney and Mobikwik, online banking and e-commerce platforms will see an increased demand in the near future as people will show willingness to move away from cash. This particularly will benefit IT startups and Fintech domains that work on online payments that enable technology processes for such companies. This also could create key requirements for technology processes for tracing financial information, eKYC form Income Tax departments. Government initiatives such as Aadhar, Jandhan will nudge a lot of Fintech companies to enable financial institutions and banks to adopt these facilities.

On the other hand sales at all major electronic and computer hardware retailers have hit rock bottom. Unable to compete with the massive discounts and low taxation offered by online giants, like Flipkart, Snapdeal and Amazon, computer retailers are forced to decrease their margins and offer freebies to walk-in customers. Currently, retailers profit from a 3%-5% margin on laptops, desktop computers and accessories. The adoption of cashless transactions through debit cards or credit cards eats into this margin as the retailer has to pay 1.8%-2% bank commission on each transaction. This has already resulted in significant slowdown of demand across PC, tablet PC and Mobile devices.

6. Conclusion:

The action of the Indian government to eradicate the four social problems- black money, corruption, counterfeiting and terrorist funding was a very bold move but it definitely affected the many parts of the economy. Due to demonetization, the first thing that happened in India was it curbed the purchasing power of most of the people. So this in turn decreased the overall trade in the country. It can be said that demonetization will create cash crunch and liquidity crisis causing inconvenience to the general public in short-term, but it will prove to be beneficial to the economy in long run on aspects like government revenue, increase in deposits, low interest rates on loans, and decline in inflationary pressure etc. Government can now easily track unreported income resulting in reducing of corrupt practices and money laundering. But it is also to be noted that the ultimate objective of demonetization to flush out black money from the economy may not be achieved, until the actual people behind black money are targeted. Moreover, people have invested their black money in assets like real estate and gold; therefore it becomes difficult on government's part to track black money. The success of demonetization depends upon the formalization by the government which will hopefully change the mindset of people to refrain from illegal activities and black money. Demonetization technically is a liquidity shock; a sudden stop in terms of currency availability. The intensity of demonetization effects clearly depends upon the duration of the liquidity shocks.

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